

Ethogram for horse ear movement characteristics, indicative of arousal / vigilance level, mood and personality

Behaviour

1. Movement in one or both ears - short travel and fast / flicky

2. Movement in one or both ears - short travel and slow

3. Movement in one or both ears - long travel and fast / flicky

4. Movement in one or both ears - long travel and slow
